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Co-seismic Landslide Susceptibility Assessment Using a Modified Newmark Model: A Case Study of the 2016 Mw 6.7 Imphal Earthquake

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Abstract

The North Eastern Region (NER) of India is one of the most seismically active zones, where earthquake-induced landslides pose a major threat to the settlements, infrastructure, and livelihoods. **Objectives:** The objectives of this research are to assess the co-seismic landslide susceptibility in the Imphal area of Manipur, Northeast India, by incorporating the effect of earthquake-induced ground motion into the slope stability analysis using the modified Newmark Sliding Block Model. **Background:** The critical gap in landslide susceptibility research in the Imphal region of NER is the lack of earthquake triggering in physically based slope stability modelling. **Methods:** The Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) data for the Mw 6.7 Imphal earthquake (January 4, 2016) were collected from the USGS database and converted to Peak Horizontal Acceleration (PHA) at the ground surface using the non-linear site response relationship for National Earthquake Hazards Reduction Program (NEHRP) site class D conditions. A Deterministic Seismic Hazard Approach (DSHA) was considered to simulate the scenario-based ground motion input to the slope stability analysis model. The critical factor of safety (F_{sc}) was computed by integrating the effect of seismic acceleration and terrain parameters, particularly slope gradient, into the slope stability analysis using the modified Newmark model. **Findings:** This study highlights a scenario-based co-seismic landslide vulnerability; the M 6.7 Imphal earthquake shows PGA ranging from 0.1 to 0.24 g with highest intensities near the epicenter, and 70.2% of the area is moderately susceptible, 18.3% low, and 11.5% highly susceptible, showcasing priority areas for hazard mitigation during future M ≥ 6.7 earthquake events. **Novelty:** The novelty of this research is that it uses a physically based co-seismic landslide susceptibility analysis that incorporates the role of seismic forces in the analysis of slope instability, as opposed to the conventional approaches that are based on the terrain parameters alone.

Keywords: Co-seismic; Landslide Susceptibility; Modified Newmark Model; Earthquake; Imphal

1 Introduction

The northeastern region of India is located in the Eastern Himalayas and is one of the most seismo-tectonically active regions in the world⁽¹⁾. Geologically, the NE region lies at the convergent plate boundary between the Indian and the Eurasian tectonic plates in the north resulting in the creation of the Himalayan mountains and an active subduction zone in the Indo-Burmese ranges along the eastern boundary of the country. The region has a complex geology and tectonic setting⁽¹⁾. The North Eastern India region also constitutes features like the Brahmaputra valley, Bengal Basin, Mishmi Hills, Shillong-Mikir Plateau, and Tripura fold belt^{(1), (2)}. Due to its complex seismo-tectonic settings, the NE region is now placed under seismic zone VI (highest risk) as per IS 1893:2025⁽³⁾, making the region highly vulnerable to earthquake-induced hazards. Earthquake activity is frequent in the northeastern region (NER) of India, and as a result moderate to large magnitude earthquake events occur repeatedly across the region, making the region highly prone to earthquake-induced secondary hazards such as landslides, etc. Landslides are threats in mountainous settings, where seismic vibrations and shaking can destabilize slopes and trigger landslide occurrences. Earthquake-induced landslides often disrupt transportation, damage infrastructure, and pose a threat to settlements, causing inconvenience and economic losses to communities. Earthquake-induced landslides occur when the stability of slopes is reduced by strong ground motions, particularly in the areas with steep slopes, weathered geological formations, and a high level of erosion. Landslides triggered by earthquakes occur when intense seismic shaking (ground motion) overcomes the shear strength of materials (soil & rocks), resulting in mass wasting. Ground shaking increases during seismic events, resulting in an increase in driving forces while reducing the resisting forces, often leading to slope failures in steep or unstable terrains⁽⁴⁾. Also, earthquakes are not only responsible for destabilization of slopes but may also permanently decrease the shear strength along discontinuities within the slope⁽⁵⁾. The above-listed geomorphological and geological conditions are observed in many parts of the NER (North Eastern Region). One such area is Imphal, the capital of Manipur, which is situated within the Imphal Valley, and is characterized by steep hill ranges formed as a part of the Indo-Burmese Mountain system (Figure 1). The area is characterized by steep slopes, weathered rocks, and intense monsoonal precipitation, which collectively contribute to slope instability and the proneness of the region to landslide hazards.

The Imphal region in Manipur, India, has experienced several moderate- to strong- magnitude earthquake events as it is located in the vicinity of the active Indo-Burmese tectonic belt. Historical records reveal that multiple earthquakes with magnitude greater than 6 occurred in and around the Imphal region and adjoining areas of Myanmar, including earthquake events such as the 1930 Imphal earthquake of M 6.2, the 1957 Kakching earthquake of M 6.2, the 1984 Churachandpur earthquake of M 6.0, and the 1988 Manipur-Myanmar earthquake of M 7.3. Numerous small magnitude earthquake events are frequently occurring in this region, indicating persistent seismic activity in the region. In areas where earthquakes occur frequently, the estimation of co-seismic landslide hazards becomes crucial. To estimate the susceptibility of slopes prone to failure, several methods have been developed. Among them, the Newmark sliding block method is widely used to estimate potential slope displacement under seismic shaking. This approach models a slope as a rigid block resting on an inclined plane and estimates permanent displacement when earthquake-induced acceleration exceeds the resisting forces of the slopes⁽⁶⁾.

The latest developments in the field of landslide susceptibility analysis have incorporated various statistical, machine learning, and hybrid approaches for the analysis of landslides. The research work carried out in the Manipur region has mainly focused on terrain and environmental factors, whereas the seismic aspects of landslides have not been considered, which is considered to be a research gap in the field of landslide analysis. The physically based models, like the Newmark Sliding Block Model, have been successfully used to assess the slope stability due to seismic activity by estimating permanent displacement. Recent research (2024-2025) has improved this method by incorporating machine learning algorithms^{(7), (8)}. However, there is a lack of research on this method in Northeast India. Recent studies in Manipur have focused primarily on landslide susceptibility along major national highway corridors such as NH-150 and NH-102 B, as well as regional-scale assessments incorporating methods like AHP, GIS-based modelling, and deep learning^{(9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14)}. While these studies considered terrain and environmental parameters, they largely neglected the effect of seismic triggers. Given that Manipur is situated within a tectonically active region associated with the Indo-Burmese tectonic belt, the crucial role of earthquake-induced ground motion in slope stability studies cannot be ignored. Thus, including seismic parameters into landslide susceptibility assessment is important, especially in regions frequently experiencing moderate to large earthquake events. This highlights the urgent requirement of co-seismic landslide susceptibility studies to better understand and mitigate co-seismic landslides in the region. In this connection, the 2016 Imphal earthquake of M 6.7, which struck approximately 29 km west of Imphal, is an interesting and crucial case study for evaluating the risk of earthquake-induced landslides in the region. Hence, this study applies the modified Newmark sliding block model to evaluate the susceptibility of slopes to co-seismic displacement in and around the Imphal region. Therefore, the objectives of this study are the following:

1. deterministic seismic hazard assessment (DSHA) to estimate scenario-based ground motions for the 2016 Imphal earthquake;
2. estimation of co-seismic slope stability by integrating seismic acceleration and terrain properties by applying the modified Newmark's sliding block model; and
3. to map co-seismic landslide susceptibility in order to identify areas prone to future earthquake-induced slope failures.

Fig 1. Study area map showing 60 Km buffer around the M 6.7 earthquake event occurred on 2016/01/04 near Imphal, Manipur.

2 Data and Methodology

This study used CartoDEM, 10-meter resolution digital elevation model, which is generated and achieved by the NRSC (National Remote Sensing Centre) on Bhuvan portal (<https://bhuvan.nrsc.gov.in/home/index.php>). The digital elevation model

(DEM) is used for deriving slope. Additionally, Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) data from the USGS for the M 6.7 Imphal earthquake on January 4th, 2016, were used. These datasets were integrated together to estimate the factor of safety and assess co-seismic landslide susceptibility using the modified Newmark's model.

A modified Newmark sliding block model⁽¹⁵⁾ is adopted to assess co-seismic landslide susceptibility in the area of interest. Traditional Newmark's model directly calculates factor-of-safety based on geotechnical properties of rocks (cohesion, friction angle, etc.), but this study focuses on estimating critical factor-of-safety (FSc) required to prevent slope failure under the effect of peak ground acceleration (PGA). The modified Newmark model integrates peak ground acceleration (PGA) with crucial terrain characteristics, especially slope, to evaluate the stability of slopes at the regional scale, as earthquake shaking intensity can be used as a proxy for estimation of vulnerable slopes in the absence of geotechnical parameters.

This study incorporates a deterministic approach for seismic input characterization by selecting a representative earthquake event based on the principles of DSHA (Deterministic Seismic Hazard Analysis). DSHA focuses on a particular ground motion generated by a specific earthquake event, referred to as the worst-case-scenario earthquake⁽¹⁶⁾. The 2016 M6.7 Imphal earthquake fulfills the criteria, as it represents a recent event of large magnitude that occurred in the vicinity of the Imphal region. Therefore, this earthquake event is selected for the scenario-based study to assess vulnerable slopes under seismic shaking. The peak horizontal ground acceleration (PGA) dataset was downloaded from M6.7, 2016/01/04, from the USGS earthquake catalog⁽¹⁷⁾. Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) values derived from this event are being used in the calculation of the factor of safety. However, PGA at the surface can be estimated using site amplification relationships where direct ground motion datasets are not available⁽⁶⁾. These values were then considered equivalent to peak horizontal acceleration (PHA) for evaluation of slope stability under seismic shaking.

The stability of slopes under seismic conditions is generally estimated by the factor-of-safety (FS), which depends upon the geotechnical and geomorphological properties of the rocks and soils. Parameters such as shear strength of rocks/soils, drainage conditions, land use/land cover characteristics, soil density, and slope-gradient play a vital role in determining the stability of slopes. The static factor of safety can be estimated using traditional Newmark's method. The stability of a slope is determined by its static factor of safety against an earthquake. Hence, the co-seismic landslide hazard in this study is estimated in terms of the critical static factor-of-safety (FSc) required to prevent the initiation of a slide during earthquake events.

The study is based on the Newmark sliding block approach, which portrays that the soil mass is most likely to collapse as a rigid block on an inclined surface. This approach explains the slope failure occurs when driving forces outweigh resisting forces.

The Newmar- based co-seismic landslide susceptibility was carried out using a modified approach, in which slope stability is estimated under seismic loading conditions. PGA (Peak Ground Acceleration) values corresponding to the 2016 Imphal earthquake were taken from the USGS (United States Geological Survey). The PGA values were directly used as an alternative to PHA.

$$FSc = \left(\frac{PHA}{\sin\alpha} \right) + 1 \quad (1)$$

2.1 Estimation of Peak Horizontal Acceleration (PHA)

Peak Horizontal Acceleration (PHA) at the ground surface was calculated from Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) values available at the bedrock level. The PGA values employed in this study were obtained from the USGS earthquake catalogue⁽¹⁷⁾ have developed a non-linear site amplification technique, which is used to estimate peak horizontal acceleration (PHA) at ground level from the PHA at bedrock level.

The ground level PHA was estimated using the following equation:

$$PHA = Ybr * Fs \quad (2)$$

Where Ybr is the PGA at bedrock level and Fs represents the site amplification factor.

Raghu kanth and Iyengar (2007)⁽¹⁸⁾ have developed an equation to calculate amplification factor (Fs).

$$\ln Fs = a_1 Ybr + a_2 \ln \delta s \quad (3)$$

Where a_1 and a_2 are site-class specific regression coefficients, Ybr is the bedrock PGA, and δs is the site amplification parameter.

According to the NEHRP (National Earthquake Hazards Reduction Program) site classification, the Imphal region falls under the site class D (stiff Soil) conditions^{(19), (20)}. These parameters were entered in the equation (3) to estimate amplification factor (Fs). The estimated the amplification factor was then added to the equation (2) and the bedrock PGA values to obtain ground level PHA values. These peak horizontal acceleration (PHA) values were used as the seismic driving force in the modified

Newmark Sliding Block method to estimate the crucial factor of safety. After estimation of the Peak Horizontal acceleration (PHA) at the ground level, the values were then used to estimate the critical factor of safety (FSc) of the slopes under seismic shaking.

3 Results & Discussion

The co-seismic landslide susceptibility analysis in the 60 km buffer zone (Figure 1) of the 2016 Imphal earthquake demonstrates that slope instability is largely affected by earthquake-induced ground shaking. Newmark's sliding block model produces a distinct spatial pattern of susceptibility identified across the study region. Peak ground acceleration (PGA) across the study area shows values ranging from 0.1 g to 0.24 g. The highest values of PGA were concentrated close to the epicenter, gradually decreasing with distance. It is observed that relatively higher PGA values in the range of 0.18-0.24 are distributed across the valley region of Imphal. However, the valley region is characterized by gentle to nearly flat slopes, which significantly reduces the likelihood of earthquake-induced landslides. Under such conditions, high ground motion may cause huge infrastructural damage, as observed during the 2016 Imphal earthquake⁽²¹⁾. The distribution of factor of safety (FSc), estimated using PGA values and slope angle, demonstrates a considerable variation across the study area. Lower factor of safety observed in the hilly terrain, where steep slopes combined with moderate to high ground acceleration decreases slope stability. Conversely, high factor of safety values are associated with low-gradient regions such as Imphal Valley, where slopes are gentle to flat. The results explain that slope gradient plays a crucial role in controlling stability, as steep slopes require less seismic acceleration to reach failure conditions. The co-seismic landslide susceptibility is derived from the factor of safety (FSc); areas with FSc values close to 1.0 were classified as highly susceptible, indicating slopes that are unstable or near to failure. Areas with $1.2 \leq \text{FSc} < 1.5$ were classified as moderately susceptible, showing marginally stable slopes that may undergo failure under seismic shaking, and the areas with $\text{FSc} \geq 1.5$ were classified as low susceptibility, indicating stable slopes with a lower possibility of earthquake-induced failure. The results (Figure 2) show that 70.02% of the areas fall under moderate susceptibility, 18.3% under low susceptibility, and 11.5% under high susceptibility. Areas below 10 degrees of slope were considered flat surfaces, as such low-gradient terrains are unlikely to undergo significant co-seismic sliding. Distance from the epicentre does not indicate the spatial pattern of susceptibility. The spatial distribution of landslide susceptibility indicates the combined influence of ground motion and lithology. The variation in PGA is controlled by the local rock and soil conditions that control seismic wave propagation and amplification.

This highlights the combined effects of terrain characteristics and earthquake-induced ground motion in governing co-seismic slope stability. As compared with previous studies conducted in the Imphal, Manipur region, which primarily focused on methods like AHP, GIS-based modelling, and machine learning techniques, the present study has an advantage in that it incorporates earthquake triggering mechanisms. Previous studies focused on susceptibility along transportation corridors and regional scales, considered static terrain and environmental factors, and did not take earthquake-induced forces into consideration^{(9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14)}. As a result, such approaches may underestimate hazard severity in seismically active zones. In contrast, Newmark's sliding block method in this study enables the physically-based estimation of slope stability under seismic shaking. By incorporating ground acceleration as driving forces, the model provides a more reliable representation of co-seismic slope behavior. This method not only refines susceptible zones but also highlights areas that may remain undetected under traditional approaches. The outcome of this study emphasizes that tectonically active regions require dedicated co-seismic landslide hazard assessments, as earthquake-induced ground motion can significantly influence slope stability. The results of this study are particularly relevant for town planning and hazard mitigation in vulnerable mountain regions, where the interaction between seismic forces and topography plays a vital role in disaster risk.

The present study reveals that landslide susceptibility due to co-seismic events in the Imphal region is influenced by the combined effect of seismic acceleration and terrain characteristics. Among these factors, slope gradient was identified as the most important factor controlling landslide susceptibility^{(22), (23), (24), (25)}. This result is in accordance with recent research results, which suggest that terrain factors control landslide events to a greater degree than seismic acceleration^{(26), (27), (28), (29)}.

However, recent developments in landslide susceptibility assessment have increasingly adopted ML and hybrid models. For example, studies that combined the Newmark model with ML models, such as XGBoost, Random Forest, etc., have shown increased accuracy in landslide susceptibility assessment, with AUC values ranging up to 0.96^{(30), (31), (32)}. This is due to the combination of physical factors, such as factor of safety and seismic acceleration, with ML models. Similarly, SHAP (Shapley Additive explanations)-based ML models and sampling optimization models have shown increased accuracy in landslide susceptibility assessment, ranging up to 8–9% compared to conventional models^{(33), (34)}. However, this is highly dependent on the availability of sufficient data, which is a limitation in regions such as Northeast India.

On the contrary, the present study follows a deterministic approach based on physical modeling with a modified Newmark model, which does not demand large training sets of data. Unlike other data-driven models, which are often associated

with interpretability issues and dependence on large sets of data, the proposed approach directly models the mechanics of slope failure due to seismic forces. Recent hybrid modeling approaches also recognize the effectiveness of incorporating Newmark parameters, as they significantly improve the performance of landslide models compared with the use of other static environmental variables, thereby recognizing the role of physical modeling in landslide modeling⁽³⁰⁾.

In addition, recent advances in landslide modeling, such as transfer learning and physics-informed modeling, have also addressed the issues of data scarcity and transferability, thereby improving the accuracy of landslide models by up to 15%⁽³⁵⁾.

When compared to the research carried out in the past in the Manipur region, which was mainly focused on static susceptibility mapping through AHP, GIS, or machine learning algorithms^{(9), (10), (11), (12), (13), (14)}, the current research includes seismic triggering mechanisms^{(36), (37), (38), (39)}. This is a major advancement over the traditional approaches, as they might result in a lower level of hazards in tectonically active regions due to the absence of seismic triggering.

The uniqueness of this research is its capability to offer a physically interpretable and regionally flexible framework for co-seismic landslide susceptibility mapping. The inclusion of seismic acceleration in the assessment of slope stability enables a more realistic simulation of landslide hazards. The dominance of PGA by slope gradients is also a major contribution of this research, as it can prove to be highly beneficial while carrying out land-use planning and hazard zonation, especially in mountainous regions.

Fig 2. Factor-of-Safety map showing high, moderate, and low factor of safety and their area wise distribution in pie-chart.

4 Conclusion

The current study demonstrates the efficacy of the modified Newmark Sliding Block Model in assessing co-seismic landslide susceptibility assessment in the Imphal region of Manipur. By combining earthquake-induced ground motion into slope stability analysis, the study provides a more realistic depiction of landslide hazards in seismically active regions. This study has demonstrated the applicability of the modified Newmark sliding block model for co-seismic landslide susceptibility assessment in the Imphal region. From the results, 70.2% of the region is classified as having moderate susceptibility, 18.3%

has low susceptibility, and 11.5% has high susceptibility. The analysis reveals that while high PGA values are concentrated near the earthquake epicentre, slope instability is predominantly governed by terrain conditions, particularly slope gradient. Despite having recorded larger PGA values in the vicinity of the earthquake epicentre, slope instability is influenced by terrain characteristics, i.e., slope gradients. Regions with higher slope gradients have lower factor of safety values, thus being highly susceptible to co-seismic landslides, whereas regions with lower slope gradients are stable even for strong ground motion.

The traditional landslide susceptibility studies mainly rely on static terrain and environmental parameters. The current method offers a remarkable improvement by incorporating a seismic triggering mechanism. This shows the importance of combining seismic parameters in landslide hazard assessments, especially in tectonically active regions such as Northeast India. The results of this study are crucial for infrastructure planning, hazard mitigation, and disaster preparedness in the mountainous regions where the interaction between geomorphology and seismic forces plays a crucial role. Future research may further enhance the model by combining detailed geotechnical parameters and multi-temporal seismic scenarios to improve prediction accuracy and reliability.

The main contribution of this research is the direct inclusion of seismic triggering in co-seismic landslide susceptibility assessment, which is based on a physically based model. This study can be extended further to multiple research directions by incorporating geotechnical parameters such as cohesion, friction angle, unit mass, etc.; multiple seismic events; and a hybrid model incorporating machine and deep learning models.

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The analysis was carried out using publicly available datasets. Ground motion data corresponding to the 2016 Imphal earthquake were obtained from the United States Geological Survey earthquake catalogue. The topographic data used for slope derivation were acquired from Cartosat DEM (10 m resolution).

No clinical support, laboratory testing, or external experimental facilities were involved in this study.

Contributory Statement:

- Upendra Bhatt (Corresponding Author): Conceptualization of the study problem, software implementation, data generation, data analysis, and original drafting of the manuscript.
- Prakash Biswakarma: Research guidance, editing, and reviewing of the manuscript.

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